

Issue and challenges of Artificial Intelligence to transform Spastic children

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About 500000 children under age of 18 currently have Cerebral Palsy. Recent population based studies from the world report, prevalence estimates of Cerebral Palsy ranging from 1 to 4 per 1000 live birth or per thousand children.

The National Policy on Education 2020 advocates inclusive education in general schools for the locomotors impaired and mildly disabled children and special education for the severely handicapped children. The prime objective of the policy is children with special needs and normal children read in he same school. This provide them better exposure and social interactions leading to further success in life to fulfill this objective technology plays important role toward it.

Education of children with special needs in an area of concern in India only million out of 12 million disabled children attend school.

The IEDC scheme, launched in 1974, implemented in 15,000 schools in 26 states and Union Territories covering 65,000 disabled children, aides to provide educational opportunities for the moderately disabled children in general schools. The scheme include per school training, counseling for parent, allowances for books and stationary, uniforms, transport, reader and escort, hostel facilities and other assisting device. The scheme provide one special teacher for every eight disabled child, community involvement and a resource room in a cluster of 8 to 10 schools.

The special school for children with special needs been a prevalent mode of teaching the disabled students. Spasticity is a condition in which body muscles stiffen or tighten, preventing normal muscle movement. the muscle remain contracted and resist being bendable, thus affecting movement, speech communication and locomotion.

Spasticity is generally caused by damage or disruption to the area of brain and spinal cord that are controlling muscles and stretch reflexes. Spasticity can be harmful to growing children as it can affect muscles and joints. spinal cord injury, cerebral palsy or multiple sclerosis can have varying degree of spasticity.

There are several treatment for spasticity which help to improve quality of daily life. surgical and nonsurgical treatments are given to children on the basis of symptoms.

Cerebral palsy is a group of disorders associated with developmental brain injuries that occur during fetal development, birth or shortly after birth. It is characterized by a disruption of motor skills, with symptoms such as spasticity, paralysis or seizures. Cerebral palsy also known as “static encephalopathy” and “little disease.”

Type

Children of Cerebral palsy can be categorized into two groups.

1. Based on the group of muscle involvement are tetraplegia, paraplegia, hemiplegia
2. Based on “quality” of movement are ataxia, athetoid or dyskinetic, spastic.

Artificial Intelligence for Spastic Children.

To educate spastic is really a titanic task in front of us. efforts have been made to provide proper and necessary education to them.

AI is a process of making intelligent machines that are similar to human intelligence, mimicking the problem solving and decision making capabilities of the human mind. AI development includes maps and navigation tools, automation tools, facial detection devices and chatbots. For those with a disability, products such as voice recognition devices can be helpful to help individuals communicate.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the curricular practices with Artificial Intelligence for spastic children prevailing in the institutions.
2. To analyze these practices on the basis of
 - a) Age of the child
 - b) I.Q. of the child
 - c) their utility in day to day life
3. To give suggestions for improvement of the curricular practices with the help of Artificial Intelligence.

Need

The current population of Lucknow district according to 2011 is 4,00,20,000. including of CP in India as reported by spastic society of Bombay is 0.2 percent or one child per thousand. thus estimated population of cp in lucknow 2,700 and there is lack of institute in lucknow for disabled and out of which there are only one or two institute providing education for the children suffering from Spasticity. to study the curriculum practices being followed at these institutes and to give suggestions to bring necessary changes, if required, to fit the curriculum as per the need of hour, the need of this study has been realized.

Delimitation

1. Due to lack of sufficient no of the schools, only four schools selected which are only representative of Lucknow city.
2. Chetna and Pyassum institutes provides its services to many kinds of disabled children but the research was focused on Spastic children only.
3. There are many other practices such as medical and the research is limited in curricular practice.

Methodology

The nature of the research is qualitative. and researcher has been followed by the Direct observation method.

The sample of the four institutes Chetna, Jyotikiran, Pyassum and Asha jyoti school of lucknow, because only these are giving education to Spastic children, hence the sampling technique used is purposive.

Tool

This study has necessitated selection of questionnaire as a tool.

Observation table has been prepared to note down the information after observation of these institutions.

Finding and conclusion

The study has been undertaken to know the curriculum practice with AI adopted by these institutes giving education to disabled with the focus on Spastic Children, for this purpose observation schedule has been prepared to study the facilities /resource available both the

physical and human ,also curriculum and co-curricular activities in the institutes.a questionnaire has also prepared to know how the transaction of curriculum with AI is been done.

It has found through collected information that the curriculum for these children is less than the normal children.even though it is heavy for these children.The teacher feel that syllabus needs improvement even though they find the present syllabus partially successful in making the Spastic child adjusted.

Co-curricular activities and cultural programmes are the essential part of the curriculum of these spastic children.language that is english and hindi, math,science and drawing are the main subjects taught to the elementary level student.in these practices communication devices can be helpful with understanding the meaning of different languages and communicating this to others, that make student more dependable.

It is found that AI systems are beginning to support therapy for children.So many devices buit by TCS rapid lab which can help in cognitive speech algorithms to convert communication by children with neurological conditions into speech,incorporation not just their native language.

The most important thing to be noticed that educational task in every class is different for different student matching with their needs and abilities which can ease their learning.

Function, in which spastic children performs are also organized for the common public.Such AI are help in the emotional and social adjusted of these children.Such AI also create awareness among the spastic children toward the abilities of these children.

Co-curriculum activities are planned in such a way which not only motivate them but also make them feel self confident for example fish catching game ,in which some fishes of iron are kept in water and stick with a magnet on one side is given to the child and asked to catch the fish.The magnet attract the iron fish and child feels that he has caught the fish and feeling develops in him that he too perform task with the perfection.AI can developed happiness among children by achieving small goals.

It has been observed and found these institute are open to accept their criticism in healthy way. To bring improvement in the curriculum they accept suggestion of the teacher and parents also.

It has emerged from the study that the curriculum of these children is same for everyone but it can be moulded according to the abilities of cp children. The admission in these institute are given to those cp children who has fail in mild to moderate category irrespective of their age . thus in same class their may be big age differences between any two children. It is known that cp children may not suffer from low I.Q.In these institute the I.Q. of almost all students fall

between 90-110 i.e. average. hence we can say that the educational tasks are set according to the abilities and capabilities of the learner (c.p. child). It must be remembered here that I.Q. remains constant but age change. Educational task should be given to a children according to their age viz a seven year old child with IQ 90 to 110 can not be given the same task as to a child of the same IQ but 12 year years old, as the 12 years old child would have more real life experiences than the younger one.

As far as the utility of curricular practices in day to day life is concerned, it can be pointed out that is very useful.

The training of cp children of keeping themselves clean, drinking, eating, behaving in socially acceptable manner and guiding the parents to handle these children with the same patience and in the same they are handled in the institute, plays a vital role in developing a child as a self-dependent. AI assisted technology help students to achieve these day to day life activities. Every act cleaning, eating, drinking and behaving in socially acceptably manner is a part of day to day life.

The subject like language Hindi, English, Math, Dwing and G.k. are very useful in day to day life. Language helps them in understanding other. AI communication device for speech impaired children designed by TCS has brought to parents of kids with Spastic children. First of its kind customized mouse keypad with output. these are providing multiple options for communication based on the child's motor skills.

If they can expressing themselves knowledge of math will help them in dealing effectively in society where no body can cheat them economically G.K. makes them aware of everything. Drawing develops a sense of appreciation for the beautiful and colorful things AI can make create environment which make them ability to do such curriculum activities.

Co-curricular activities and cultural activities like singing, dancing etc. keep them in touch with art and society and develops their aesthetics sense. They can enjoy the latest songs and interact with other on its various aspects.

The way they are motivated and made self confident helps them in performing their day to day task.

SUGGESTIONS

REGARDING CURRICULUM

1. curriculum should be more objective and precise to make it qualitatively improved with AI.

2. curriculum should be in accordance with limitations of the cp. children.
3. Hobby courses should also be introduced, keeping in view the varied interests of the c.p. children
4. content in the books should be presented in attractive manner viz colorful printing .colourful pictures
5. content should be presented in logical and psychological sequence.
6. language of the content should simple and easily understandable to these children with languages supported AI
7. Supplementary manual regarding the curriculum practices to the teachers should also be provided.
8. curriculum should be flexible enough to make adjustable with the classroom requirements.

Suggestion regarding quality of the teacher

1. teacher for teaching cp children should be trained to teach and handled these children
2. they should be provided good salary i.e. at par with teachers of normal children.
3. they should dedicated and self motivated to work for these kinds of children
4. teachers should be given proper incentives to motivate them to do their best
5. teachers should be informed time to time to improve their teaching methods and encouraged to go for innovative teaching style
6. orientation programs and refresher courses can also be organized for teachers.

Suggestion regarding equipment/instrument

1. attractive and colorful teaching aids e.g. overhead projector, video, audio ,cassette player etc. should be in schools and teachers should also be made acquainted with it's user. AI plays crucial role.
2. familiar technical supported staff can be appointed .A big/sufficiently big playgrounds must be the school premises.

3. various types of equipments necessary for facilitating the learning of cp children should also be here in the school.

Suggestion regarding co-curriculum

1. A series of planned co-curriculum activities should be introduced to make cp children self dependent

2. Co-curricular and cultural activities should be integrated effectively with the study of the subjects to make the learning process interesting and effective.

3. more exposure should be given these children for public performance which will work as a confidence and morale booster.

Suggestion regarding vocational education

1. vocational education should be introduced in Jyoti kiran also.

2. vocational education should be started from as early age as possible.

3. a recruitment facilitation/placement cell should also be opened.

5. After vocational training cp children should be helped to establish their own, small production unit.

6. the products produced during the vocational training should be sold in open market, which would be helpful in earning some money for own development.

Suggestion regarding community resources mobilization

1. By organizing meetings and services community should be made aware to understand the difference between cp children and other disabled children.

2. They should be asked to work and donate generously without any greed.

3. community should be encouraged to purchase the products made by these children

4. community should be involvement/limited to the functions in which these children perform.

5. attempts should be made to identify various resources available in community. these resources can be utilized for the growth and development of the institution.

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